

CELLULAR AND INTRACELLULAR REGENERATION. CURRENT ASPECTS

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Abstract

Regeneration refers to the process by which organisms repair and replace damaged or lost cells, tissues or organs. This process is essential for maintaining health. Regeneration can occur in several ways, depending on the type of tissue or organ and the severity of the injury. Some cells, can replace quickly, while other cells, can be much more difficult to replace or regenerate. Cellular regeneration refers to the process by which cells replace damaged or lost ones. This process can be different depending on cell type and tissue, as some cells may have a greater ability to multiply and replace than others. Intracellular regeneration refers to the process by which cells can repair their individual cellular components, such as proteins, organelles, or damaged DNA.

The article represents a narrative synthesis of specialized literature, with the aim of explaining the mechanisms of cellular and intracellular regeneration that take place in the human body.

Keywords: differentiation, epithelia, hypertrophy, myocardium, proliferation, regeneration, stem cells.

Mechanisms of cellular and intracellular re-generation

Regeneration consists of two distinct stages – proliferation and differentiation. These stages are more obviously expressed in the case of cellular regeneration. At the proliferation stage, young and undifferentiated cells multiply. These cells are called cambial cells (lat. cambium – "change") or stem cells. In the differentiation stage, young cells mature and improve structurally and functionally. This modification, of increasing ultra-structure by differentiation (or maturation), is the main mechanism of regeneration at the intracellular level. As

regeneration occurs at the intracellular level, the restoration of tissue structure and function can occur at different levels (repair of DNA, formation of new enzymes, increase in the number of mitochondrial cristae, enlargement of ER cisternae, synthesis of new mitochondria, ribosomes, etc.). [2,14]

Classification of tissues according to the form of regeneration

In phylogeny and ontogeny, the structural and functional specialization of tissues has led to selection favoring a predominantly cellular form in some tissues, a predominantly or exclusively intracellular form in others (Table 1). [12]

Table 1

Forms of regeneration in various tissues

Cellular regeneration	Intracellular regeneration	
Bone tissue Epithelial tissues Loose connective tissue Hematopoietic tissue Lymphoid tissue	Predominantly cardiac tissue	Exclusively the central nervous system (pyramidal, ganglion cells, etc.)

In some tissues such as epithelial or hematopoietic ones, the cellular form of regeneration is predominant over the intracellular one. In simple terms, the process by which these tissues are regenerated involves cell division, followed by the differentiation and specialization of some of the resulting daughter cells. After cell division, undifferentiated daughter cells remain in an undifferentiated state and act as reserve stem cells. As old cells age and die, stem cells begin to divide to produce new daughter cells. Following this division, one of the daughter cells differentiates and specializes to take over the role of the dead cell, while the other remains as a stem cell. Thus, the number of stem cells is kept constant, ensuring constant tissue regeneration and repair. [2,8]

In the case of the central nervous system (including ganglion cells and pyramidal cells) and myocardium, intracellular regeneration is the sole or predominant form of regeneration, and these tissues lack stem

cells. In these cases, the cells that are in the process of differentiation lose their ability to proliferate irreversibly, which leads to a stability of the total number of cells. Over time, part of the cells die irreversibly through apoptosis, and this process intensifies with the aging of the body. [2,8,12,14]

Cellular regeneration of epithelia

Epithelial tissues are normally in a state of continuous renewal, and their regenerative capacities are very high and are achieved through the mitotic proliferation of stem cells, that is, at the cellular level. The skin epithelium has the highest capacity for regeneration at the cellular level. [8,12]

Through cell division, epithelial stem cells produce new cells that differentiate into mature epithelial cells similar to those lost. Stem cells in stratified epithelium are found in the basal layer, whereas in monolayer epithelium, such as that of the small intestine, they are located in the crypts. In the case of mesothelium,

stem cells are among the mesotheliocytes. The ability of most epithelia to regenerate serves as the basis for their rapid recovery process under pathological conditions, known as reparative regeneration. [12,15,16]

A constant physiological regeneration takes place in the glands as they carry out their secretory activity. Merocrine and apocrine glands contain long-lived cells, and their regeneration after secretion occurs by intracellular regeneration processes and sometimes by proliferation. In contrast, in holocrine glands, regeneration occurs through the division of stem cells from the excretory ducts, and the new cells, through differentiation, become glandular cells. [8,12]

Epidermal stem cells (EpiSCs) are primarily responsible for the regeneration of this tissue, as they

have the ability to differentiate into several cell types. EpiSCs have the ability to multiply indefinitely and are mainly located in three separate areas: in the basal layer of the epidermis, in the bulb area of the hair follicle, and at the base of the sebaceous glands. The stem cells in the basal layer are responsible for the development of keratinizing epithelial cell lines under physiological conditions and ensure regeneration in case of superficial damage to the epidermal covering. The other group of stem cells is responsible for the development of superficial epitheliocytes, hair and glands, and is involved in the regeneration of deep and extensive skin lesions (pic.1). [9,12,13,16,19]

Pic.1. Location of epidermal stem cells

Stem cells have the ability to differentiate into a variety of specialized cells, but they also divide to maintain a constant number of similar stem cells through symmetric or asymmetric division (pic.2). In the asymmetric division model, a stem cell generates a

differentiated cell and another stem cell. On the other hand, under the symmetric division model, one stem cell produces either two differentiated cells or two stem cells. [11,18,19]

Pic.2. Asymmetric and symmetric division of stem cells

Growth factors and cytokines play an important role in the regeneration process of epithelial lesions. In the inflammation stage of wound regeneration, neutrophils release cytokines such as interleukin (IL)-1 α , IL-1 β and tumor necrosis factor (TNF)- α , which have the role of attracting and activating other cells, as well as intensifying the inflammatory process. Macrophages subsequently move to the affected area, eliminate pathogens, promote the migration of EpiSCs and keratinocytes, and induce extracellular matrix (ECM) synthesis by secreting cytokines and growth factors such as transforming growth factor (TGF)- α - β , fibroblast growth factor (FGF) and platelet-derived growth factor (PDGF). After the lesion is completely covered by a layer of keratinocytes, the molecular signals responsible for proliferation stop. After that, the keratinocytes stratify to gradually restore the damaged epidermal layer. [13,19]

Intracellular regeneration of the myocardium

Even though significant progress has been made in the early diagnosis and prevention of cardiovascular diseases, their prevalence is increasing globally. Heart failure in particular is a major problem, being the leading cause of death, disability and financial costs. About

38 million people worldwide are affected by this condition. Typically, the heart does not work properly after an injury that affects blood flow. This problem occurs because heart cells cannot be replaced once they have been destroyed, due to the fact that they cannot multiply in adulthood. According to estimates, only a small fraction – less than 1% of the heart cells in an adult's heart regenerate each year. [1,7,10]

During embryonic and fetal development, heart growth is primarily determined by the mitotic division of cardiac cells. These cells are generated either by differentiation of cardiac progenitors or by proliferation of already existing cardiac cells. The process of cardiac cell proliferation during fetal development is essential for the proper formation of cardiac structures, including maturation of the ventricular wall. After birth, the myocardium begins to expand in volume, but soon there is a transition to cardiac hypertrophy, which involves an increase in the size of the cardiomyocytes instead of an increase in their number. This leads to the exit of myocardial cells from the cell cycle. During this transition, cardiomyocytes undergo cell cycle changes, including acytokinetic mitosis (nuclear division without cell division), and endoreduplication (increasing the number of DNA copies without nuclear division and cellular) (pic.3). [3,4,5,6,19]

Pic.3. Cell cycle variations in CM after birth

Physiological regeneration of myocardial cells occurs at the intracellular level and is characterized by high intensity and speed, due to the high pressure exerted on the myocardium. This regeneration is further intensified during intense physical exertion and in conditions of pathological conditions such as heart defects or hypertension. In such cases, the components of the

sarcoplasm of myocardial cells constantly degrade, being replaced by newly formed ones. With the increase in the load exerted on the heart, both hypertrophy (increase in size) and hyperplasia (increase in number) of the organelles, including myofibrils, sarcomeres, mitochondria, etc. appear. This process leads to cardiomyocyte hypertrophy (pic.4). [4,8,10,17]

Pic.4. Hypertrophy of the myocardium: a – normal myocardium; b – hypertrophied myocardium

At an early age, cardiomyocyte polyploidization occurs and binuclear cells appear. Myocardial hypertrophy is characterized by adaptive growth corresponding to its vascular bed. In pathological conditions, such

as heart defects that cause hypertrophy, this adaptation does not occur, and after a certain time, due to malnutrition, some of the affected cardiomyocytes die and are replaced by scar tissue (pic.5). [4,8,10]

Pic.5. Post-infarction cardiosclerosis

When heart muscle tissue is damaged, for example in the case of injury or myocardial infarction, there are no stem cells that can replace the lost heart cells. Instead, the processes of regeneration and adaptation occur intracellularly in the neighboring cardiomyocytes, which hypertrophy and take over the function of the dead cells. This is called reparative regeneration of cardiac muscle tissue which also occurs in focal or diffuse dystrophy. Instead of dead cardiomyocyte cells, a scar of connective tissue (also called post-infarction cardiosclerosis) is formed (pic.5). [8,10]

Conclusions

Regeneration is classified as cellular, when active mitotic division of stem or adult cells occurs to restore the structure and function of damaged tissue; the intracellular one, is characterized by the proliferation or hypertrophy of intracellular components to increase the compensation capacity in stress situations. Cellular regeneration is characteristic of tissues that are in a continuous state of renewal, for example the epidermis of the skin and the mucosa of the digestive tract. These tissues are constantly exposed to the aggressive action of external and internal factors, therefore, they rapidly regenerate due to stem cells, which proliferate to replace old cells. Intracellular regeneration is specific to tissues where cells have lost the capacity for mitotic division and stem cells are absent. For example, the myocardium cannot restore the number of cells lost in case of injury, partial recovery occurs due to hypertrophy of the remaining cells, and the defect is replaced by a scar.

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